

EFFECT OF INTEGRATED NUTRIENT MANAGEMENT ON PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL/SOIL ANALYSIS OF RICE

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Abstract

The present study conducted to evaluate the suitable proportion of organic manures and inorganic fertilizers along with biofertilizer to maximize growth and dry matter accumulation of rice on alkaline soils of Uttar Pradesh, India. The experiment consisting twelve treatments viz., T₁ (control), T₂ (75% RDF), T₃(100% RDF), T₄ (125% RDF), T₅ (100% RDF+FYM 6 t/ha), T₆ (100% RDF V. C.3t/ha), T₇ (100% RDF+BGA @10kg/ha), T₈ (100% RDF+ neem cake 6q/ha), T₉ (75% RDF+FYM 6 t/ha)k T₁₀ (75% RDF+V.C.3t/ha), T₁₁ (75% RDF+BGA 10Kg/ha) and T₁₂ (75% RDF+ neem cake 6q/ha) were tested in Randomized Block replicated as thrice. The variety NDR-359 was taken as test crop. The experimental soil was silty alkaline in texture having pH (1:2.5) 8.58, EC 0.41 dSm⁻¹, organic carbon (2.4mgkg⁻¹), Available N (170.50), P (8.81), K (215.52), S (8.97 kg ha⁻¹) and Zn (0.63 ppm). Nutrient uptake of N, P and K was maximum in treatment modules having 100% RDF + 3 tonne vermi compost followed by 100% RDF+ 6 tonne FYM. The substitution of 25 % nitrogen may through any organic source of nutrient. The higher availability of nutrient N, P and K content in soil after harvest were recorded under all the INM modules as compared to inorganic fertiliser application treatments.

Key words: integrated nutrient management, rice, yield, yield attributes

Introduction

Rice (*Oryza sativa* (L.)) is one of the most important staple food crops in the world. In Asia, more than two billion people are getting 60-70 per cent of their energy requirement from rice and its derived products.

Rice is the bulk of food security of the global population. In 21st century there will be the need of about 250 million tons of food grains to feed the rapidly increasing population. The global requirement of rice by 2050 AD world by 800 million tones, which is 26% higher than the present level of production.

Uttar Pradesh is an important rice growing state in the country. The area and production of rice in this state is about 13.84 million hectare and 14.00 million tonnes respectively with productivity of 2358 kg per hectare (Anonymous, 2013). Organic resources are largely biological in origin and they have several nutrients in their composition which on decomposition are released in to soil. The organic materials are available in abundance in eastern U.P. at normal cost and may be used in integrated manner with nitrogen fertilizer. FYM improves soil physical, chemical and biological properties of soil. FYM contains 0.5% N, 0.2% P₂O₅ and 0.5% K₂O. It supplies all major nutrients (N, P, K, Ca, Mg and S) necessary for plant growth, as well as micronutrients (Fe, Mn, Cu and Zn). FYM application leads to a better environment for root development also improves soil water

holding capacity, the fact that the use of organic fertilizers improves soil structure, nutrient exchange, and maintains soil health has raised interests in INM or organic farming.

Nitrogen is one of the most important elements and has more pronounced effect on growth, and development as well as on quality of rice than other elements, however, excess quantity of nitrogen lowers the quality. Integrated nutrient management involves conjunctive use of nitrogenous chemical fertilizer and organic manures which have the great significance for increasing the productivity, quality and sustainability of rice as they supply all macro and micro nutrients in balanced and required proportion as far as the crops need. Integrated nitrogen management not only economizes the use of chemical fertilizers but also sustain the soil health by improving physico-chemical and biological conditions of rhizospheric soil for longer period than inorganic nitrogen alone (Krishana et al., 2005).

Materials and methods

The field experiment was conducted during Kharif 2014 and 2015 at Agronomy Farm of Narendra Deva University of Agriculture and Technology, Narendra Nagar (Kumarganj), Faizabad (U.P.). The experimental site located at Kumarganj is situated 42 km away from Faizabad city on Faizabad-Raibarely road.

Table-3.4: Treatments detail:

T ₁	Control
T ₂ -	75% RDF
T ₃ -	100% RDF
T ₄	125% RDF
T ₅	100% RDF+FYM 6 t/ha
T ₆	100% RDF V. C.3t/ha
T ₇	100% RDF+BGA @10kg/ha
T ₈	100% RDF+neem cake 6q/ha
T ₉	75% RDF+FYM 6 t/ha
T ₁₀	75% RDF+V.C.3t/ha
T ₁₁	75% RDF+BGA 10Kg/ha
T ₁₂	75% RDF+neem cake 6q/ha

Physical analysis:

Bulk density Bulk density was determined with the help of soil core method given by Richard, (1960).-

$$BD = \frac{\text{Wt. of oven dry soil core}}{\text{Field volume of sample}}$$

Nitrogen content and uptake:

The processed straw and grain samples were digested with concentrated H₂SO₄ in presence of catalyst mixture modified Kjeldahl method was adopted for determination of nitrogen content in straw and grain as described by Jackson (1973). The percentage

of nitrogen was multiplied with grain and straw yield obtain nitrogen uptake in seed and content in plant respectively.

$$\text{Nutrient uptake (kg/ha)} = \frac{\text{Nutrient content in grain \%} \times \text{Grain yield (kg/ ha)}}{100}$$

$$\text{Nutrient uptake (kg/ha)} = \frac{\text{Nutrient content in straw \%} \times \text{Straw yield (kg/ha)}}{100}$$

Phosphorus content and uptake:

The ground grain and plant samples were digested with di-acid mixture having nitric and per chloric acid and determined by vanadomolybdo phosphoric yellow colour method (Jackson 1973). The percentage of phosphorus was multiplied with grain and content in plant to obtain phosphorus uptake in grain and content in plant respectively.

$$\text{Nutrient uptake (kg/ha)} = \frac{\text{Nutrient content in grain \%} \times \text{Grain yield (kg/ha)}}{100}$$

$$\text{Nutrient uptake (kg/ha)} = \frac{\text{Nutrient content in straw \%} \times \text{Straw yield (kg/ha)}}{100}$$

Potassium content and uptake:

The plant samples were digested with di-acid mixture and determined separately by using flame photometer (Jackson, 1973). The percentage of potassium content was multiplied with grain and straw to obtain uptake of potassium in grain and straw respectively.

$$\text{Nutrient uptake (kg/ha)} = \frac{\text{Nutrient content in grain \%} \times \text{Grain yield (kg/ha)}}{100}$$

$$\text{Nutrient uptake (kg/ha)} = \frac{\text{Nutrient content in straw \%} \times \text{Straw yield (kg/ha)}}{100}$$

Protein content in grain:

Percentage of protein content in grain was estimated by assaying total nitrogen (Kjeldahl method) and protein content was computed by multiplying the nitrogen with factor 6.25 (AOAC, 1970).

Soil analysis:

Chemical properties

pH:

Soil pH was determined with the help of glass electrode pH meter in 1:2.5 soil water suspensions as described by Jackson (1973).

Electrical conductivity:

Electrical conductivity was determined with the help of electrical conductivity meter in 1:2.5 soil water suspensions as described by Jackson (1973).

Organic carbon (g kg⁻¹):

Organic carbon was determined with the help of Walkley and Black's rapid titration method as advocated by Walkley and Black's (1934).

Available nitrogen (kg ha⁻¹):

The available nitrogen content in soil samples was determined by alkaline permanganate method as described by Subbiah and Asija (1956).

Available phosphorus (kg ha⁻¹):

The available phosphorus in soil determined by Olsen's method as per procedure described by Olsen *et al.* (1954).

Available potassium (kg ha⁻¹):

The available potassium in soil was determined by Morgan's method as advocated by Jackson (1973).

Result and Discussion

Soil pH and EC

The maximum reduction in pH and EC was noticed under treatment T₅ (100 % RDF + FYM 6t/ha) followed by T₆ (100% RDF + VC 3t/ha) which might be due to the production of organic acid from FYM and green manure decomposition resulting lowering of this property. The application of FYM and vermin compost increased the formation of humic acid and humus soil and these decrease the soil pH and Electrical conductivity. The reduction in EC of the soil with application of FYM, and vermicompost may ascribed to salt leaching facilitated by improved permeability of soil and formation of weak salts as a result reduction in electrical conductivity. The maximum reduction in pH with organic manure might be due to formation of organic acid during decomposition of organic manure which neutralized the sodium salt present in soil and increase the hydrogen ion concentration. These results closely corroborate with the findings of Prasad and Singhanian (1989), Koushal *et al.* (2011), Kumar *et al.* (2006) and Datta *et al.* (2008).

Organic carbon

It is clear from the table that the maximum buildup of organic carbon was observed with application of treatment consisting T₅ (100 % RDF+ FYM 6t/ha), T₅ (100% RDF + VC 3t/ha) and T₈ (100% RDF + neemckae 6q/ha). Application of FYM, vermicompost and neemcake increase humus carbon in soil. Better crop growth was observed with vermicompost and FYM treated plots might be due to the improvement of physical and chemical properties of the soil and providing good soil environment to plant and enhance root growth leading to accumulation of more organic residues in the soil while its increase with the treatment combination is ascribed to direct incorporation of organic matter through organics. These results closely corroborates with the findings of Prasad and Singhanian (1989) and Kumar *et al.* (2007).

Porosity, Bulk density and Water holding capacity of soil

Integrated use of organic, inorganic and biofertilizers sources improved soil porosity and water holding capacity decreased bulk density in post largest soil. the maximum increase in soil porosity and water holding capacity was noticed with treatment T₆ (100% RDF + VC 3t/ha). The water holding capacity increase due to granulation and formation of more capillary pores through addition of FYM and vermicompost. These results collaborates with the finding of Kumar and Tripathi (2006).

Perusal of data showed that lowest bulk density measured with the treatment T₆ while highest measured with treatment T₁ have been no fertilizers. Addition of the FYM or vermicompost reduced the bulk density. The bulk density of soil decreased due to improved volume of pore space because addition of vermicompost and FYM which ultimately reduced the bulk density of soil.

Availability of N, P and K

Data on availability of N, P and K as affected by various nutrient management modules showed that the available nutrients caused in soil.

Available of Nitrogen

The maximum buildup of available nitrogen was recorded with the application of 100% RDF + FYM 6t/ha followed by 100% RDF and VC 3t/ha. The decline in available nitrogen seemed to be associated with the mobilization of fertilizer, taken by the crop and its leaching from the plough layer (0-20 cm). Application of FYM and Vermicompost along with inorganic source of nutrient increased available N in soil. The increment in available nitrogen soil might be due to release of extracellular nitrogen substance and biological fixation of atmospheric nitrogen. Among the different sources of organic manure and biofertilizer because of its fast decomposition and solubility effect on native soil nutrients which led to better availability of nutrients besides, improving the soil environment. The

increase in available nitrogen content with the incorporation of organic source along with inorganic source may be attributed to nitrogen mineralization from organic manure. The most soluble soil condition under organic source might have helped the mineralization of soil N and buildup of higher available nitrogen. The results also corroborates by (Swarup and Yaduvanshi, 2013 and Sharma *et al.* 2009).

Available phosphorus

The available phosphorus in soil increased significantly with the application of 100% RDF + FYM 6t/ha along through inorganic fertilizers. This might be due to favorable soil condition by the application of organic manure which increased activity of microbes and thereby increase in available phosphorus status of soil. Similar findings were observed by Singh *et al.* (1997), Subashini *et al.* (2007), Tadesse *et al.* (2013) and Tilathi *et al.* (2012). They also reported that the available phosphorus was improved with the application of different combination of RDF with FYM, green manure and BGA.

Available potassium

It is clear from the data that the available K status in soil after harvest of rice crop varied due to the application of various combination of organic and inorganic source of nutrient. These results clearly indicated that the appreciable increase in available K was noted over control. The maximum build up available K was observed under the treatment having T₅ (100% RDF + FYM 6t/ha) followed by T₆ (100% RDF + VC 3t/ha). The application of organic manure might also be attributed to the direct addition of potassium in the available K pool of the soil. Similar findings were also observed by Kumar *et al.* (2007), Datta *et al.* (2008), Singh *et al.* (2005) and Singh and Singh (2007).

Summary and conclusions:

The build up of neutral soil pH, EC and OC were recorded under INM modules as compared to sole inorganic fertilizer treatment (T₅) whereas, maximum reduction in pH was observed with the application of T₅ (100% RDF + FYM 6t/ha). Whereas, the maximum build up of organic carbon also recorded with the application of the treatment T₅ (100% RDF + FYM 6t/ha). The integrated organic, inorganic and biofertilizers sources improved soil porosity and water holding capacity and decreased bulk density in post harvest soil. The maximum increase in soil porosity and water holding capacity was noticed with the application of 100% RDF + VC 3t/ha during both the years of investigation. The higher availability of nutrient N, P and K, in soil after harvest were recorded under all the INM modules as compared to inorganic fertilizer application treatments. Whereas the maximum availability of N, P and K were estimated under the treatment having T₅-100% RDF+ FYM 6t/ha which was closely followed by T₆ and T₄.

On the basis of present investigation, it can be concluded that the T₆-100% RDF + VC 3t/ha found most effective and maintaining soil health for sustainable rice production.

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Table 1: Effect of integrated nutrient management on nitrogen and phosphorus content grain and straw of rice crop .

Treatment		Nitrogen content (%)				Phosphorus content (%)			
		Grain		Straw		Grain		Straw	
		2013-14	2014-15	2013-14	2014-15	2013-14	2014-15	2013-14	2014-15
T ₁	Control	1.25	1.27	0.42	0.42	0.35	0.36	0.14	0.15
T ₂	75% RDF	1.33	1.35	0.44	0.45	0.37	0.38	0.15	0.16
T ₃	100% RDF	1.37	1.39	0.46	0.46	0.38	0.39	0.16	0.16
T ₄	125% RDF	1.41	1.44	0.47	0.49	0.40	0.41	0.18	0.17
T ₅	100% RDF+FYM 6 t/ha	1.40	1.41	0.48	0.48	0.41	0.42	0.16	0.17
T ₆	100% RDF V. C.3t/ha	1.42	1.43	0.49	0.47	0.42	0.43	0.18	0.17
T ₇	100% RDF+BGA @10kg/ha	1.37	1.38	0.46	0.46	0.38	0.38	0.14	0.16
T ₈	100% RDF+neam cake 6q/ha	1.39	1.39	0.48	0.45	0.38	0.39	0.14	0.16
T ₉	75% RDF+FYM 6 t/ha	1.34	1.36	0.44	0.44	0.39	0.37	0.16	0.16
T ₁₀	75% RDF+V.C.3t/ha	1.35	1.38	0.43	0.46	0.37	0.39	0.17	0.16
T ₁₁	75% RDF+BGA 10Kg/ha	1.33	1.35	0.42	0.43	0.35	0.36	0.16	0.16
T ₁₂	75% RDF+neam cake 6q/ha	1.29	1.31	0.40	0.44	0.36	0.35	0.15	0.15
	SEm±	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.01
	CD at 5%	0.06	0.07	0.02	0.05	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.02

Table 2: Effect of integrated nutrient management on total N uptake grain and straw and straw of rice crop.

Treatment		N uptake (Kg ha ⁻¹)				Total N uptake (Kg ha ⁻¹)	
		Grain		Straw		2013-14	2014-15
		2013-14	2014-15	2013-14	2014-15		
T ₁	Control	28.44	29.78	13.57	13.99	42.01	43.77
T ₂	75% RDF	47.37	49.21	22.10	23.13	69.47	72.34
T ₃	100% RDF	63.99	63.12	30.30	29.45	94.29	92.57
T ₄	125% RDF	72.43	75.50	33.80	35.97	106.23	111.47
T ₅	100% RDF+FYM 6 t/ha	75.47	76.41	35.97	36.16	111.44	112.56
T ₆	100% RDF V. C.3t/ha	79.24	80.72	36.91	35.82	116.15	116.54
T ₇	100% RDF+BGA @10kg/ha	71.61	73.76	33.18	33.93	104.79	107.69
T ₈	100% RDF+neam cake 6q/ha	71.18	72.89	33.92	32.57	105.10	105.46
T ₉	75% RDF+FYM 6 t/ha	64.12	63.44	28.84	28.12	92.96	91.56
T ₁₀	75% RDF+V.C.3t/ha	65.89	65.03	29.38	30.35	95.28	95.37
T ₁₁	75% RDF+BGA 10Kg/ha	61.19	61.98	26.47	27.05	87.67	89.02
T ₁₂	75% RDF+neam cake 6q/ha	58.46	60.59	24.47	27.47	82.94	88.06
	SEm±	2.52	2.84	1.03	1.93	2.80	3.75
	CD at 5%	9.38	10.32	3.03	5.67	11.23	11.00

Table 3: Effect of integrated nutrient management on total P uptake grain and straw and straw of rice crop.

Treatment		P uptake (Kg ha ⁻¹)				Total P uptake (Kg ha ⁻¹)	
		Grain		Straw		2013-14	2014-15
		2013-14	2014-15	2013-14	2014-15		
T ₁	Control	7.96	8.44	4.52	4.99	12.49	13.44
T ₂	75% RDF	13.18	13.85	7.53	8.22	20.71	22.07
T ₃	100% RDF	17.75	17.71	10.54	10.24	28.29	27.95
T ₄	125% RDF	20.55	21.50	12.95	12.48	33.49	33.97
T ₅	100% RDF+FYM 6 t/ha	22.10	22.76	11.99	12.81	34.09	35.56
T ₆	100% RDF V. C.3t/ha	23.44	24.27	13.56	12.96	37.00	37.23
T ₇	100% RDF+BGA @10kg/ha	19.86	20.31	10.10	11.80	29.96	32.11
T ₈	100% RDF+neam cake 6q/ha	19.46	20.45	9.89	11.58	29.35	32.03
T ₉	75% RDF+FYM 6 t/ha	18.66	17.26	10.49	10.23	29.15	27.49
T ₁₀	75% RDF+V.C.3t/ha	18.06	18.38	11.62	10.55	29.68	28.93
T ₁₁	75% RDF+BGA 10Kg/ha	16.10	16.53	10.09	10.06	26.19	26.59
T ₁₂	75% RDF+neam cake 6q/ha	16.32	16.19	9.18	9.37	25.49	25.55
	SEm±	0.74	0.94	0.38	0.46	0.89	0.97
	CD at 5%	2.47	2.76	1.12	1.36	2.60	2.85

Table 5: Effect of integrated nutrient management on pH, EC, OC in soil after harvest of rice crop.

Treatment		pH		EC		OC (gkg ⁻¹)	
		2013-14	2014-15	2013-14	2014-15	2013-14	2014-15
T ₁	Control	8.50	8.45	0.27	0.26	0.36	0.37
T ₂	75% RDF	8.35	8.30	0.26	0.25	0.35	0.36
T ₃	100% RDF	8.32	8.27	0.25	0.24	0.38	0.38
T ₄	125% RDF	8.25	8.20	0.25	0.24	0.39	0.39
T ₅	100% RDF+FYM 6 t/ha	8.15	8.10	0.25	0.25	0.41	0.43
T ₆	100% RDF V. C.3t/ha	8.20	8.15	0.25	0.24	0.44	0.45
T ₇	100% RDF+BGA @10kg/ha	8.30	8.25	0.25	0.24	0.41	0.42
T ₈	100% RDF+neam cake 6q/ha	8.30	8.25	0.25	0.25	0.39	0.41
T ₉	75% RDF+FYM 6 t/ha	8.35	8.30	0.26	0.25	0.41	0.42
T ₁₀	75% RDF+V.C.3t/ha	8.40	8.35	0.26	0.25	0.40	0.41
T ₁₁	75% RDF+BGA 10Kg/ha	8.40	8.35	0.25	0.26	0.38	0.39
T ₁₂	75% RDF+neam cake 6q/ha	8.42	8.34	0.25	0.25	0.37	0.38
	SEm±	0.27	0.32	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01
	CD at 5%	0.80	0.95	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.04

Table 4: Effect of integrated nutrient management on potassium content grain and straw of rice crop.

Treatment		Potassium content (%)			
		Grain		Straw	
		2013-14	2014-15	2013-14	2014-15
T ₁	Control	0.40	0.41	1.28	1.29
T ₂	75% RDF	0.42	0.43	1.36	1.37
T ₃	100% RDF	0.44	0.44	1.40	1.41
T ₄	125% RDF	0.45	0.47	1.44	1.49
T ₅	100% RDF+FYM 6 t/ha	0.45	0.47	1.44	1.49
T ₆	100% RDF V. C.3t/ha	0.45	0.47	1.44	1.49
T ₇	100% RDF+BGA @10kg/ha	0.44	0.44	1.40	1.41
T ₈	100% RDF+neam cake 6q/ha	0.44	0.44	1.40	1.41
T ₉	75% RDF+FYM 6 t/ha	0.42	0.43	1.36	1.37
T ₁₀	75% RDF+V.C.3t/ha	0.42	0.43	1.36	1.37
T ₁₁	75% RDF+BGA 10Kg/ha	0.42	0.43	1.36	1.37
T ₁₂	75% RDF+neam cake 6q/ha	0.41	0.42	1.32	1.33
	SEm±	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.02
	CD at 5%	0.04	0.02	0.09	0.06